

RESEARCH ARTICLE

XR-Driven Robotic System Training for Occupational Health, Safety, and Maintenance

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ABSTRACT The integration of Extended Reality (XR) technologies into Industry 5.0 offers innovative solutions for industrial training by overcoming the limitations of traditional methods, such as high costs, inefficiencies, and production disruptions. These technologies enable immersive and scalable training environments, providing workers with hands-on experience while minimizing risks and resource constraints. This study presents an XR-based training platform designed to enhance workforce skills in health and safety, robotic system operations, and maintenance through immersive Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) scenarios. Evaluated by 22 participants from diverse professional backgrounds, the platform achieved a 50% reduction in training time compared to conventional methods, while significantly improving skill acquisition and task efficiency. Participants rated immersive VR environments highly (4.4/5) for engagement and knowledge retention, with usability and instructions also scoring positively (4/5). Scenario-based performance showed the average scores in health and safety tasks (72 points), while robotic system operations (60 points) and maintenance (54 points) reflected increasing task complexity. Despite moderate cognitive demands, the platform effectively balanced mental effort with engagement, providing an accessible and effective training experience. These findings underscore the potential of XR technologies to transform industrial training by enhancing efficiency, safety, and scalability, aligning with the evolving needs of Industry 5.0.

INDEX TERMS Augmented reality, extended reality, human-robot collaboration, immersive learning, Industry 5.0, virtual reality training, workforce development and XR in manufacturing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industry 5.0 represents a paradigm shift towards human-centered production, integrating advanced technologies such as XR, robotics, and artificial intelligence to improve flexibility, collaboration, and safety in industrial environments. This shift is driven by the need to adapt to rapidly evolving production processes and meet the demands of increasingly complex tasks. However, conventional training methods are struggling to keep up with these changes. As highlighted

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by De Giorgio et al. [1], conventional training methods are not sufficient for modern industrial systems. Furthermore, Johnson et al. [2] emphasizes the risks associated with not utilizing realistic, immersive training environments. This gap in traditional training methodologies underscores the need for innovative solutions that can better align with the demands of Industry 5.0.

XR encompasses AR, VR, and mixed reality (MR), each offering unique levels of immersion. VR provides a fully virtual environment, AR overlays digital content onto the real world, and MR blends virtual and real elements interactively. XR technologies present a promising solution to

address the limitations of traditional training methods. These technologies create immersive, customizable, and safe learning environments, enabling workers to engage with virtual machines and environments that replicate real-world conditions.

VR-based training, for example, reduces costs and simplifies complex setups by allowing participants to interact with virtual machinery, eliminating the need for costly physical equipment. This approach not only enhances user confidence but also minimizes errors and reduces the time spent on actual machinery, making training processes more efficient and cost-effective [3]. Moreover, XR technologies are particularly beneficial in scenarios where equipment is unavailable or when working under hazardous conditions. Their ability to simulate risky tasks provides a safer, more scalable alternative to real-world training environments. However, one limitation of VR training is the lack of tactile feedback, which can hinder learning effectiveness compared to hands-on interaction with physical machines [4]. While VR provides a controlled training environment, its ability to replicate real-world tactile experiences remains limited [5].

Beyond cost reduction, XR training enhances skill acquisition and operational efficiency by offering personalized, adaptive learning environments [3]. From a social perspective, XR technologies support a more inclusive approach to workforce development by making training accessible to a broader range of individuals, regardless of location or availability of physical equipment. This is especially important in industries that require specialized skills, as XR can help bridge the gap by providing workers with realistic, hands-on experience without the risks associated with real-world training. Additionally, XR-based training has been shown to improve motivation and overall user experience compared to traditional methods, making it a preferred choice for industrial training [6], [7]. While the potential benefits are clear, there are still challenges that need to be addressed. Over-guidance in XR training environments can lead to cognitive overload, negatively impacting memory and performance. Research has shown that while well-designed guidance improves outcomes, excessive assistance can be detrimental [8]. Moreover, user experience issues, such as fatigue and discomfort during VR sessions, suggest that better hardware design is necessary to ensure long-term comfort for users [9].

Despite these challenges, XR training provides an efficient, scalable solution that allows workers to acquire new skills more quickly and safely. As noted, XR technologies also allow for real-time learning, making it easier for workers to adapt to evolving industrial technologies [10]. However, some aspects of XR training, such as the impact of different types of guidance on learning outcomes and error rates, remain underexplored. The level of guidance provided during training can significantly affect performance [8]. Advancements in XR should focus on improving the realism of virtual interfaces, enhancing the recognition of worker behaviors, and developing techniques for collaboration and information

sharing. Moreover, cloud-based collaboration approaches are essential for enabling multi-user remote interactions and ensuring effective coordination within shared systems [5].

This study specifically focuses on orientation training in industrial contexts, aiming to enhance the practical skills and safety competencies of workers using XR technologies. It explores the application of AR and VR technologies in training for robotic arm operation and maintenance, aiming to improve learning outcomes, provide hands-on experience, and enhance safety protocols without interrupting production processes. The training platform was used to train 22 participants across three carefully designed scenarios. Scenario 1, Health and Safety, focused on hazard identification and the application of safety protocols in a virtual industrial environment. Scenario 2, Robotic System Introduction, introduced participants to the components and functions of robotic systems. Scenario 3, Robotic Maintenance, provided a simulated environment for troubleshooting and performing routine maintenance tasks on robotic systems. To evaluate the effectiveness of this training approach, participants completed pre-training assessments to measure their baseline knowledge of topics such as robotic maintenance and occupational safety. After training, participants were evaluated through post-training tests, which measured learning progress, task completion times, and cognitive load using the NASA-TLX survey. Additionally, an open-ended, SUS (System Usability Scale)-inspired user experience questionnaire was administered to gather qualitative feedback, helping to identify areas for improvement and insights for advancing the system. The results indicate that XR-based training significantly enhances learning outcomes across different scenarios, particularly in safety and technical training. Participants demonstrated improved task performance, reduced completion times, and maintained a balanced cognitive load. These findings underscore the potential of XR technologies to enhance industrial training by improving efficiency, safety, and cost-effectiveness while bridging the gap between theoretical learning and practical application. These findings underscore the potential of XR technologies to enhance industrial training by improving efficiency, safety, and cost-effectiveness while bridging the gap between theoretical learning and practical application.

The rest of the paper presents this XR-based training platform for robotic arm operation and maintenance in Industry 5.0. “Related Work” reviews XR applications in industrial training, their limitations, and categorizes existing research into three main areas: industrial safety and training, engineering and manufacturing training, and cognitive load and training methodologies. “System Description” details how the platform developed and explained three scenarios. “Test and Results” evaluates system performance in enhancing learning and safety. “Discussion” highlights benefits and scalability, while “Limitations” address hardware and user challenges. “Conclusion and Future Work” summarize findings and propose enhancements like haptic feedback and expanded scenarios.

II. RELATED WORK

In this study, the existing research has been examined under three main topics within the educational content: occupational health and safety, introduction to robotic systems, and maintenance. Each topic has been analyzed further in the context of VR, AR, MR. Additionally, aspects such as the role of XR technologies in engineering and other educational processes, as well as their application in training for production processes, have been explored under separate subsections. This approach provides a comprehensive perspective on the broad applications of XR in the field of education.

A. THE ROLE OF XR TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY TRAINING

Occupational health and safety (OHS) training has found a natural partner in XR, which uses realistic yet controlled environments to teach essential skills without exposing trainees to real-world dangers. In practice, Kaarlela et al. [11] utilized AR-based digital twins to depict risky scenarios, integrating interactive elements that encourage deeper engagement and sharpen hazard recognition. Such solutions are particularly valuable in high-stakes industries, where major machinery, complex production lines, or hazardous materials present continuous risks.

Building on earlier efforts to refine OHS practices, Moser and Schlager [12] introduced an XR framework tailored to industrial safety training, demonstrating how immersive simulations can both increase knowledge retention and cut down on accidents stemming from inadequate procedures. Because trainees can virtually rehearse tasks, everything from routine safety inspections to swift emergency responses becomes more intuitive. The modular structure of VR training has also been demonstrated in safety applications by Dianatfar et al. [13], as seen in the TAU laboratory-developed VR modules, which were successfully adapted for Whirlpool with minimal modifications, requiring only language localization and security scanner integration.

While XR-based training enhances engagement, Domgue et al. [14] found that AR, VR, and video-based fire safety training differed in effectiveness. AR improved knowledge acquisition but was outperformed by VR and video, though it excelled in long-term retention. Its effectiveness could be enhanced with more interactive and realistic elements.

Although XR brings a host of benefits—like real-time feedback and customizable settings this approach still faces hurdles, including hardware expenses, the need for precise motion tracking, and the challenges of maintaining stable performance over prolonged sessions. Companies with limited budgets or older technologies may feel strained when attempting to implement high-end XR solutions.

B. ADVANCEMENTS IN XR-BASED TRAINING FOR INDUSTRIAL ROBOTICS

Industrial robotics training often involves expensive equipment, intricate programming, and a narrow margin of error.

XR environments address these issues by offering safe, repeatable conditions where learners can refine their skills. For example, Praticò and Lamberti [15] found that VR-based exercises for emergency procedures simplified complex drills, though users sometimes experienced a higher mental load. Nevertheless, being able to simulate critical errors without damaging machinery, or endangering users, can substantially lower training overhead.

Likewise, Hořejsí et al. [16] discovered that VR contributed to faster mastery of assembly tasks by eliminating real-world constraints and letting trainees repeat certain procedures multiple times with minimal risk. A recurring challenge, however, is the lack of haptic feedback—manipulating virtual objects feels less intuitive than handling physical components. Niedermayr et al. [17] tackled this issue by incorporating sophisticated tool simulations and responding quickly to user actions through visual or auditory cues. Their work indicates that while digital approximations of physical sensations can't replicate real-world touch, they can still significantly reinforce users' mental models.

Meanwhile, Almeida et al. [18] explored a metaverse-inspired approach that allows trainers to design specialized industrial simulations without extensive programming expertise. By lowering barriers to content creation, the authors pave the way for more widespread use of XR in settings where hands-on training may be too costly, risky, or logistically complicated. Yang et al. [19] further bridged the gap between virtual and tangible environments by merging MR with digital twins, letting trainees interact with fully integrated robotic systems in real time. This strategy can reduce mechanical failures triggered by operator mistakes, as users gain an in-depth understanding of how technology behaves under different conditions.

Zawadzki et al. [20] found that smart factories see fewer mistakes and more efficient operations when staff are trained with VR modules yet underscored the need for robust calibration and precise modeling to accurately represent real-world processes. Gong [21], on the other hand, emphasized the difficulties of blending XR into older production lines—factories relying on legacy systems may face serious compatibility obstacles. Despite these limitations, expanding XR adoption in robotics holds the promise of both safer work environments and more efficient, scalable training programs.

C. XR APPLICATIONS IN MAINTENANCE

Maintenance tasks, particularly in large-scale industries, can be unpredictable and potentially hazardous. Often, malfunction scenarios are too rare or too costly to stage repeatedly for instructional purposes, which makes them prime targets for XR-based simulations. Winther et al. [22] showcased how immersive pump maintenance training enabled users to grasp multi-layered repair procedures without risking expensive damage or resource-intensive downtime. Yet, the researchers found that purely virtual environments lacked physical cues, causing slower performance and occasional

mistakes. A blended approach that integrates real tools or tangible objects with virtual overlays may offer the best of both worlds.

Continuing this line of investigation, Zhang et al. [23] highlighted how VR can be a cost-effective and engaging alternative to traditional maintenance training—especially beneficial for tasks requiring high precision or those performed in hazardous locations. However, if VR setups are too cumbersome, poorly optimized, or incompatible with existing workflows, they can discourage adoption. Looking forward, researchers and developers are working to refine VR user interfaces and incorporate haptic or motion-based hardware to bridge the gap between digital learning and real-world execution.

D. OTHER APPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES OF XR

Beyond robotics and maintenance, XR finds a home in diverse fields such as education, manufacturing, and even medical training, though each domain introduces unique demands. Khlaif et al. [24] observed notable academic improvements among engineering students learning through XR simulations, but also pointed to the importance of stable, high-performance infrastructure to avoid frustrating technical glitches. Similarly, AlGerafi et al. [25] concluded that XR fosters interactive and motivating learning experiences, though hardware costs and connectivity limitations can hinder widespread use.

Alnagrat et al. [26] championed virtual labs for their safer, more flexible format, indicating that these digital settings could translate well to industrial contexts with the right modifications. Meanwhile, Kim et al. [27] focused on user-centric design streamlined interfaces, ergonomic visuals, and carefully chosen color schemes to reduce discomfort during extended sessions. In real-world production lines, Novikov et al. [28] cautioned that legacy systems might need large-scale upgrades before they can handle the data-intensive demands of XR, although these investments could pay off in terms of reduced errors and improved throughput.

Looking at skill development, Naranjo et al. [29] demonstrated that well-crafted XR modules not only promote faster learning but also help refine the manual dexterity of trainees faced with precision tasks. Caputo et al. [30] explored more cost-conscious XR implementations using hand-tracking and simpler hardware, showing encouraging results while emphasizing the continued importance of accurate feedback loops. Given the myriad applications, it's clear that the success of any XR initiative depends on a balanced approach that considers hardware constraints, software sophistication, and user readiness.

Addressing cognitive load stands out as a pivotal concern in XR-based training. Stanneya et al. [31] recommended adaptive learning systems that adjust difficulty levels or offer supportive cues based on a learner's current performance, thus preventing mental overload. Rettinger et al. [32] underscored that a mix of guided tutorials and open-ended

exploration can ease the burden on trainees while maintaining engagement. However, Bailey et al. [33] discovered that novices and experts often have different needs: a single XR approach may overwhelm beginners yet fail to challenge advanced users. These differences highlight the importance of flexible instructional design, something XR is well-equipped to support.

Finally, Kim et al. [34] brought attention to non-technical issues like data privacy, system compatibility, and security measures. As XR platforms gather more user data—ranging from motion profiles to biometric indicators—safeguarding this information becomes paramount. Ensuring robust encryption and consistent security protocols is crucial for maintaining user trust and meeting regulatory requirements. By tackling these concerns in tandem with improving user interfaces, refining hardware, and tailoring content to different learning levels, the XR community can reinforce its potential as a transformative tool that transcends traditional industrial training boundaries.

E. ALIGNMENT WITH RELATED WORKS AND CONTRIBUTION

Building upon the existing body of literature, this study focuses on reducing XR training duration through a modular scenario-based approach that minimizes excessive guidance while maintaining effectiveness. Additionally, attention is given to cognitive overload induced by immersive technologies by not only implementing standardized assessments like NASA-TLX but also developing a more detailed set of surveys. These customized evaluations provide insights into user satisfaction, learning progression, and scenario success trends throughout the training. By integrating these elements, a more comprehensive understanding of how users adapt to XR-based learning environments and how training methodologies can be optimized for better efficiency and engagement is achieved.

III. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The proposed system combines VR and AR technologies to provide a cohesive training experience, maintaining consistency between virtual and real-world applications. The shared components between VR and AR platforms ensure consistency in the interface and functionality, with Unity Engine powering 3D modeling and physics simulations. The system tracks the user's decisions in exam mode and stores the results in a MySQL database.

During the training process, the observer plays a crucial role in guiding and supporting trainees. This individual ensures that the participants interact effectively with the system, providing assistance where needed. Throughout the training process, participant data, including scores and completion times, are recorded in the database for further evaluation. Trainees actively engage in the training sessions, interacting with the system in both VR and AR environments.

VR was developed for full immersion and interaction with virtual environments, while AR focuses on enhancing

real-world training with digital overlays and contextual guidance. The VR system is designed for the Meta Quest 3, selected for its standalone operation, high-resolution display, and inside-out tracking, which allow for efficient user movement without external sensors. Its compatibility with Unity facilitates integration with the training environment. The system incorporates INTERACT v23.11.00 Plugin, enabling interaction with virtual equipment. Additionally, Exam Mode provides real-time feedback to support skill development.

The AR application, built on Unity 2022.3.40f, enhances real-world training by overlaying virtual instructions and guidance onto physical environments. The Meta XR All-in-One SDK enables precise placement of virtual objects in real space, while custom scripts facilitate dynamic object interactions. The entire software development process follows IEEE Access 12207 and AQAP 2210 standards, ensuring compliance with industry best practices. Agile methodologies are applied to streamline development, with iterative updates improving system reliability and functionality. Visual aids like arrows, information panels, and 3D objects guide users through training tasks, and AR also incorporates virtual personal protective equipment (PPE) items for safety training. This system ensures that users can interact with both physical and virtual elements in real-time, providing a more immersive and context-rich learning experience.

TABLE 1. Training scenario structure.

Scenario 1	
Module 1:	Safety Procedures and Protocols
Module 2:	Health & Safety Issues in Human-Robot Collaboration
Module 3:	Practice
Scenario 2	
Module 1:	Introduction to Robotic Systems
Module 2:	System Startup and Shutdown
Scenario 3	
Module 1:	Troubleshooting
Module 2:	Tools to Use in Maintenance
Module 3:	Routine Maintenance (AGV)

takes place in a real-world environment (1.b), where a trainee (1.d) uses a Meta Quest 3 headset and controllers (1.c) under the supervision of an observer. Training data is stored in MySQL (1.e). On the right, the VR module, built in Unity with the INTERACT plugin (2.a), runs on a PC (2.b) via Quest Link, immersing the trainee (2.e) in a virtual environment (2.c) using a Meta Quest 3 headset (2.d). Data from VR sessions is also stored in MySQL (2.f). The source code and additional resources for the application are available on GitHub [35].

A. COMPREHENSIVE TRAINING APPROACH

Training scenarios in this study integrate comprehensive safety training with a particular focus on human-robot collaboration. This approach blends theoretical knowledge with practical, real-world applications. Through immersive simulations, participants not only learn how to interact safely and effectively with robotic systems but also acquire the technical skills needed for system maintenance and troubleshooting.

The platform provides an effective solution for occupational safety and robotic maintenance across industrial environments. By incorporating XR technologies, the platform ensures a comprehensive, interactive, and scalable training experience that addresses critical needs in industrial safety, human-robot collaboration, and maintenance training.

B. TRAINING MODULES

The training program is structured around various scenarios within a laboratory environment that simulates real-world conditions, aimed at developing the competencies required for new graduates, interns, and technicians to be oriented towards industrial robotic processes. These scenarios progressively build user competence, starting with fundamental safety practices and advancing to more technical topics.

As detailed in Table 1, Scenario 1 covers health and safety, including emergency procedures and safe navigation. Scenario 2 introduces robotic systems, focusing on sensors, safety features, and system operations. Scenario 3 addresses

FIGURE 1. System architecture.

Fig. 1 presents the architecture of the developed system, integrating both AR and VR training. On the left, the AR module, developed in Unity with the Meta XR SDK (1.a),

TABLE 2. Safety procedures and protocols.

Module Explanation	The module introduces the laboratory environment, emergency procedures, and safety protocols.
Observe the Safety Area	Identify safe (green) and hazardous (red) zones within the lab.
Pedestrian Crossing	Use designated pedestrian crossings to prevent accidents with moving equipment.
Observe the Robot	Maintain a safe distance from the robotic arm while it moves.
Watch Robot Movement	Observe the robot's movements to avoid hazards in its operational area.
Observe the Given Chassis	Focus on the robot's interaction with the chassis, avoiding movement or tipping.
Understand Barriers	Barriers protect users, with entry prohibited when robots are active.
Identifying Risks	Identify hazards, like smoke from the control unit.
Understanding Emergencies	In emergencies, press the emergency button to stop the system.
Finishing the Module	After completing safety checks, confirm adherence to protocols and proceed to the next module.

troubleshooting and maintenance, teaching fault identification and tool usage for repairs.

1) SCENARIO 1: HEALTH AND SAFETY

This scenario educates users on safety protocols in robotic environments, covering safety procedures, human-robot collaboration, and navigating safe and hazard zones. It includes training on emergency response and proper use of PPE, such as helmets and gloves, to ensure safe operations.

a: MODULE 1: SAFETY PROCEDURES AND PROTOCOLS

The initial module introduces the laboratory environment, focusing on layout, safety measures, and operational elements. It ensures users understand emergency procedures and safe navigation, providing a foundation for effective engagement.

The steps in Table 2 for Scenario 1, Module 1, provide a foundational guide to user safety and operational awareness in the laboratory. By covering safety zones, robotic movements, and emergency protocols, the module prepares users to navigate the workspace responsibly and efficiently.

b: MODULE 2: HEALTH & SAFETY ISSUES IN HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION

This module focuses on the importance of PPE and safety protocols when working with automated systems. It intro-

FIGURE 2. Robot movement and light curtain test.

TABLE 3. Health & safety procedures.

Step	Description
Go to Start Point	Move to the starting point, guided by floor indicators.
Module Explanation	Learn about potential hazards from robotic movements and the importance of PPE.
Go to the Kawasaki	Follow the safe path to reach the robot.
Observe the Laser Gate	Observe the laser gate, understanding it triggers an emergency halt when the robotic area is entered.
Observe Robot & Test Light Curtain	Watch the robot move and test the light curtain by entering the danger zone.
PPE Necessity	Learn the importance of wearing gloves to protect against cuts, burns, and injuries.
Gloves for Maintenance	Reinforce the importance of gloves for hand protection during maintenance.
Safety Glasses for Maintenance	Remember to wear safety glasses for protection from debris, chemicals, and other hazards.
Hard Hat for Maintenance	Learn that wearing a hard hat protects the head from falling objects and impacts.
Finish	The module is complete, proceed to the next.

duces key equipment like gloves, safety glasses, and hard hats, along with safety mechanisms such as laser gates and light curtains.

Fig. 2 demonstrates participants observing the robot's movement and testing the light curtain by entering the danger zone.

Table 3 guides participants through safety measures, emphasizing PPE. Activities include identifying hazards and testing safety mechanisms like light curtains, building confidence for safe robotic operation. Completing the module prepares participants for future training.

c: MODULE 3: PRACTICE

Module 3 allows participants to apply the knowledge gained in previous modules by simulating real-world scenarios. It focuses on AGV safety, tool usage, and maintenance procedures, allowing users to demonstrate their understanding and skills independently.

FIGURE 3. Identifying safe and hazardous zones.

Fig. 3 illustrates participants identifying green (safe) and red (hazardous) zones to maintain awareness of safety areas during operations.

The steps outlined in Table 4 guide users through practical safety tasks, such as observing safety zones, using PPE, and responding to emergencies. By completing these steps, users practice critical safety protocols, ensuring they are prepared for real-world applications in an automated environment.

C. SCENARIO 2: INTRODUCTION TO ROBOTIC LABORATORY

This scenario introduces participants to robotic systems, covering the safe startup and shutdown of AGVs and robotic arms while emphasizing safety. It also familiarizes users with lab components like servers, computers, and robotic arms to understand their functions.

a: MODULE 1: INTRODUCTION TO ROBOTIC SYSTEMS

This module familiarizes learners with the laboratory’s different areas, sensors, and robotic applications. Participants will learn about the environment, available tools, and operational procedures related to robotic systems and automation.

The steps in Table 5 guide users through a virtual tour of the lab, explaining key components like computers, servers, and robots. By interacting with the robot and AGV, watching instructional videos, and understanding the workflow, users gain hands-on experience, preparing them for more advanced modules.

TABLE 4. Practice and application of safety procedures.

Step	Description
Start Point	Use visual cues to reach the starting point.
Module Explanation	Apply knowledge from previous modules.
Observe the Safety Zones	Observe green (safe) and red (hazardous) zones.
Follow the Path to the Kawasaki Robot	Follow arrows to the robot, staying in safe areas.
Observe the Robot	Watch the robot’s operation from a safe distance.
Watch Robot Movement	Monitor the robot and avoid the danger zone.
Observe the Given Chassis	Be cautious of the chassis’ stability.
Understand the Purpose of Barriers	Stay out of areas surrounded by safety barriers.
Identifying Risks	Mark hazards, e.g., smoke from malfunctions
Understanding Emergencies	In emergencies, press the emergency button to stop the robot.
Observe the Laser Gate	The laser gate halts operations if breached.
Observe the Robot Movement	Stay outside danger zones while monitoring the robot.
Use Gloves	Protect hands from cuts, burns, and chemicals.
Use Safety Glasses	Protect eyes from debris and chemicals.
Use Hard Hats	Protect against impacts and falling objects.
Completion	Completed the module.

b: MODULE 2: SYSTEM STARTUP AND SHUTDOWN

Module 2 introduces participants to the operation of a robotic system, focusing on how to start, stop, and perform essential checks. It provides detailed instructions for safely initializing and interacting with the robotic environment, ensuring users understand the proper procedures for system operation.

FIGURE 4. Powering On the server switch to activate the robotic system.

TABLE 5. Introduction to robotic systems procedures.

Step	Description
Module Explanation	Understand sensors and robotic applications in the lab.
Virtual Lab Tour: Computers	Learn how lab computers connect to the server for robot control.
Virtual Lab Tour: Server	Learn the server’s role in managing robotic operations.
Virtual Lab Tour: Robot	Understand the Kawasaki RS005L robotic arm and its applications.
Virtual Lab Tour: Chassis	Observe the robot’s role in inspecting chassis welding points.
Virtual Lab Tour: Walking Area	Walk only in designated safe areas.
Interact with Robot and AGV	Interact with the robot and AGV.
Watch Chassis Inspection Video	Watch a video of the robotic chassis inspection process.
Completion of Module	Mark the completion of the module and transition to Module 2.

Table 6 outlines the steps for safely operating the robotic system, including checking emergency buttons, activating switches, and configuring components. These steps equip participants to start, stop, and maintain the system efficiently and safely.

Fig. 4 depicts the action of powering on the server switch to activate the robotic system for operation.

D. SCENARIO 3: ROBOTIC MAINTENANCE

Scenario 3 focuses on enhancing users’ robotic system maintenance skills by guiding them through the diagnosis and troubleshooting of common issues. It includes tasks like battery replacement, troubleshooting malfunctions, and using maintenance tools, along with simulations for inspecting safety components such as light curtains and emergency stop buttons.

a: MODULE 1: TROUBLESHOOTING

Module 1 in Scenario 3 introduces participants to troubleshooting procedures, focusing on identifying and resolving issues in robotic systems. This module emphasizes safe practices while diagnosing and fixing common problems that may arise during system operation.

Fig. 5 shows the process of safely removing any obstacles that are blocking the robotic system to ensure smooth operation.

Table 7 guides users in starting and troubleshooting the Kawasaki robot system, focusing on obstacle checks, light

TABLE 6. System startup and shutdown procedures.

Step	Description
Module Description	Explains how to safely start and stop the robotic system.
Checking the Emergency Button	Verify and deactivate the emergency button.
Activating the Inota and Kawasaki Buttons	Activate the AGV button for safe robot interaction.
Going to the Server	Check server connections for proper system configuration.
Turning on the Switch	Power on the server switch to start the system.
Turning on the Robotic Arm Switch	Activate the robotic arm switch to supply power.
Check the Emergency Button	Ensure the emergency button on the fence is deactivated.
Go to the Controller	Check and reset the emergency button on the controller if necessary.
Start the System via the Computer	Follow instructions to initiate the robotic system via the computer.
Stop the System	Safely halt the system using the computer’s manual instructions.
Turn off the Robotic Arm Key	Power down the robotic arm for safe maintenance.
Go to the Server:	Access the server components.
Turn Off the Server Switch	Power off the main server switch to shut down the system.
Finish	Confirm procedures and proceed to the next scenario.

FIGURE 5. Safely removing obstacles to ensure smooth operation.

curtain functionality, and software issue investigation, helping participants develop effective problem-solving skills.

b: MODULE 2: TOOLS TO USE IN MAINTENANCE

Module 2 in Scenario 3 familiarizes participants with essential maintenance tools and safety equipment, emphasizing the

TABLE 7. Troubleshooting procedures for the Kawasaki robot system.

Step	Description
Start the Kawasaki Robot System	Use the computer to initiate the robot system, following safety rules.
Identify the Problem	Check emergency buttons to ensure they are not activated.
Shutdown the System	Shut down the system remotely via the computer.
Check for Obstacles	Inspect the workspace for objects obstructing the robotic platform.
Remove the Obstacle	Safely remove any identified obstacles.
Check the Light Curtain	Ensure the light curtain is clear of obstructions.
Start the System	Restart the robotic system from the computer.
Open the Computer	Access the computer to check for software issues.
Type the Command on the Computer	Input the command sequence to resolve the issue and complete the startup.

importance of safety precautions for robotic system maintenance.

Table 8 outlines the steps for using PPE and introduces maintenance tools like nippers, pincers, screwdrivers, and multimeter. Participants will gain the practical knowledge needed to safely maintain robotic systems while following safety protocols.

c: MODULE 3: ROUTINE MAINTENANCE (AGV)

Module 3 in Scenario 3 trains participants to perform maintenance on an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV). This module walks users through diagnosing and replacing the AGV’s battery, ensuring they are prepared to handle maintenance tasks safely and effectively.

Fig. 6 illustrates approaching the Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) for maintenance and diagnosis if it stops moving unexpectedly.

Table 9 outlines the steps for monitoring AGV movement, diagnosing battery issues, and replacing the battery. By using PPE and tools like the Allen wrench and multimeter, trainees will learn to safely and accurately perform maintenance, ensuring the AGV functions properly after the replacement.

IV. TEST AND RESULTS

The “Test and Results” section details the validation study conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the training plat-

TABLE 8. Maintenance tools and safety equipment.

Step	Description
Wear PPE	Wear gloves and a hard hat for safety during maintenance.
Wear Gloves for Maintenance	Put on gloves to protect against electrical, chemical, and physical hazards.
Wear Glasses for Maintenance	Use safety glasses to shield your eyes from debris and chemical splashes.
Hard Hat for Maintenance	Wear a hard hat to guard against falling objects
Go to Toolset	Familiarize yourself with the tools in the toolset for upcoming tasks.
Observe Nippers	Learn how to use nippers to cut wires and make adjustments.
Observe Pincers	Understand how pincers securely grip components.
Observe Screws	Study screwdrivers and their application.
Observe Wrenches	Identify how wrenches are used for tightening and loosening.
Observe Multimeter	Familiarize yourself with the multimeter.
Observe Allen Wrench	Learn the use of the Allen wrench.

FIGURE 6. Diagnosing and performing maintenance on AGV.

form in enhancing participants’ skills through XR technologies. The study included 22 participants with diverse roles

TABLE 9. Routine maintenance procedures for AGV.

Step	Description
Observe AGV Movement	Monitor the AGV to identify any operational issues.
AGV Maintenance	Diagnose the AGV if it stops moving.
PPE	Wear gloves and a helmet before starting maintenance.
Check Battery Health	Use an Allen wrench to access the battery compartment.
Battery Replacement	Inspect batteries for damage.
Voltage Measurement	Measure battery voltage with a multimeter.
Remove the Batteries	Remove faulty batteries for replacement.
Use of Multimeter	Learn to properly use the multimeter for accurate voltage readings.
Insert New Batteries	Install new batteries securely in the AGV.
Close AGV Rear Cover	Reattach and screw on the rear cover after battery replacement.
Securing the AGV Rear Cover	Fasten the rear cover with an Allen wrench to protect internal components.
Final System Check	Test the AGV to confirm proper functioning after maintenance.

and experience levels, ranging from trainees to professionals. Pre-test and post-test evaluations measured improvements in knowledge, while NASA-TLX surveys assessed cognitive and physical workload. The results demonstrated significant skill enhancements, with average training durations reduced by nearly 50% compared to traditional methods, specifically the human-robot collaboration trainings previously conducted at the Intelligent Factory and Robotics Laboratory (IFARLAB) of Eskişehir Osmangazi University. Satisfaction surveys highlighted high levels of engagement and realism, though areas such as scenario-specific instructions and the inclusion of real-time feedback mechanisms were identified as opportunities for further improvement.

In these tests, participants completed the three scenarios described in the System Description section from start to finish in a VR environment. Only a brief explanation of the

TABLE 10. Pre-test previous knowledge survey.

#	Survey Question
1	Indicate if you have worked with robotic systems or arms in any capacity
2	Do you understand safety protocols in a laboratory environment?
3	Can you identify specific risks or hazards when working with automated systems or robotics?
4	Have you used PPE in industrial or laboratory settings before?
5	Have you been trained to use emergency stop functions for machinery?

system’s usage was provided, and no external assistance was offered during the training sessions. Moreover, tests were conducted within the application at the conclusion of each scenario before proceeding to the next one.

Fig. 7 illustrates the training process, which includes a Pre-Test, followed by XR Training and a Practical Exam. After the training, users complete a post-test.

FIGURE 7. Diagram of testing and results workflow in XR training.

A. VALIDATION TEST PREPARATION

The user validation study was conducted over two days at the Intelligent Factory and Robotics Laboratory (IFARLAB) of Eskişehir Osmangazi University. The study involved 22 participants aged between 18 and 37 years. The participant pool included both interns (technicians and engineers) and professionals (technicians and engineers), ensuring a diverse representation of roles and experience levels. This diversity provided insights into the system’s effectiveness across varying levels of prior expertise.

1) PRE-TEST PHASE

Before starting the user test, participants completed a “Pre-Test Previous Knowledge Survey” consisting of five questions designed to evaluate their existing knowledge prior to the training.

This survey utilized four rating scales: YES/NO, Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced. Responses marked as “NO” were categorized as Beginner for analysis. To maintain participant anonymity, only age range, current role, and prior experience with XR devices were recorded, excluding any personal information such as names, contact details, or gender. Participants were informed about data protection

TABLE 11. Post-test knowledge improvement survey.

#	Survey Question
1	Today I see myself as the following level when working with a robotic system or arm:
2	Today I have the knowledge and experience in safety protocols of laboratory environments at the level of a:
3	Today I can identify specific risks or hazards when working with automated systems or robots like a:
4	Today I have the knowledge of use and application/experience to use Personal Protective Equipment in industrial or laboratory settings at the level of a:
5	Today I have the knowledge of how to respond to emergency stop function for machinery at the level of:

measures and provided consent before participating. Table 10 presents the Pre-Test Previous Knowledge Survey, detailing the questions used to assess participants’ baseline knowledge and readiness for the training.

Participants who completed the pre-test survey proceeded to the user test sessions, which lasted between 40 and 70 minutes per session. Each session involved two participants, who conducted the tests using the Meta Quest 3 device. Each participant was assigned a unique ID for login purposes, and their training logs—including user ID, training evaluation scores, and training durations—were securely stored in the database without including any personal data.

Upon completing their sessions, participants were asked to complete a series of post-test surveys designed to evaluate their experiences and learning outcomes with the platform. The first of these was the Post-Test Knowledge Improvement Survey, comprising five questions aimed at measuring participants’ knowledge gain by comparing their understanding before and after the training. Responses were rated on a three-point scale: Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced. Table 11 provides a detailed overview of the survey questions used to assess the improvement in participants’ knowledge and the effectiveness of the training program.

The second survey, the Post-Test Learning Outcomes Survey, included 20 questions aimed at measuring the extent to which participants achieved the intended learning outcomes of the training modules. Participants rated their responses on a three-point scale: Not-at-all, to some extent, and advanced, reflecting their perceived level of progress. Table 12 outlines the survey questions, providing a comprehensive overview of the evaluation framework used to assess participants’ learning achievements following the training.

2) TEST-PHASE

This system employs a weighted scoring mechanism to evaluate user performance across exam scenarios conducted entirely within a VR environment. In our VR-based training, at the end of each of the three scenarios, targeted tasks related to that scenario were assessed as part of the exam. During

TABLE 12. Post-test learning outcomes survey.

#	Survey Question
1	I understand the importance of safety procedures.
2	I can navigate through the lab environment
3	I know the key safety areas (light curtain, inspection area) and protocols
4	I can identify potential health and safety hazards.
5	I can label potential risks when I see them.
6	I understand emergency response steps.
7	I can handle these emergencies step-by-step
8	I can follow safety guidelines and protocols
9	I know how to use my PPE.
10	I recognize physical hazards in human-robot collaboration.
11	I know how to behave and react in common collision risks and hazardous situations
12	I know typical physical hazard zones in the factory (laboratory environment)
13	I know safe distances and safe zones in the laboratory environment.
14	I can manage initial system checks and diagnostics
15	I know common sensor types and their use
16	I can follow diagnostic steps to determine issues
17	I know laboratory elements that need maintenance (AGVs and robotic arm)
18	I can run safety checks
19	I know and can use common maintenance tools and materials.
20	I can manage maintenance tasks.

the exam, no external guidance is provided, and users must rely solely on the knowledge acquired during the training modules. Each task’s successful completion is automatically recorded, and the system sums the weights of all correctly executed tasks to calculate a final score.

For instance, if a module includes procedures with weights of 10, 5, and 5 (totaling 20), successfully completing the 10-weighted procedure contributes 50 points ($10/20 \times 100$) to the final score, while each 5-weighted procedure adds 25 points if completed. Incomplete procedures receive no points. At the end of the exam, the system displays the final score to the user and stores it in the database for subsequent analysis.

3) POST-TEST-PHASE

The Post-Test Phase is comprised of three key evaluation components: the Post-Test Training Satisfaction Survey, the NASA-TLX workload assessment, and the Post-Test Feedback Survey. This phase serves as the final evaluation step,

TABLE 13. Post-test training satisfaction survey.

#	Survey Question
1	I found all the functions I needed to operate the XR application.
2	How easy was it to navigate (e.g. including the emergency exit, descriptions, indications) and use it.
3	Match between system and the real world.
4	How clear were the instructions provided during the training?
5	How relevant was the training content to your role or future tasks?
6	How adequate were the hands-on practice opportunities during the training?
7	Overall, how satisfied are you with the training you received?

capturing user satisfaction, perceived workload, and qualitative feedback regarding the overall training experience.

The Post-Test Training Satisfaction Survey aimed to evaluate participants’ overall satisfaction with the application through seven targeted questions. These questions covered key aspects such as the clarity of functions, ease of navigation, fidelity between virtual and real environments, clarity of instructions, alignment with future professional roles, adequacy of hands-on experience, and overall satisfaction. Participants rated their responses on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = lowest, 5 = highest). Table 13 lists the exact questions used to assess satisfaction and application effectiveness. These post-tests were a customized version of the System Usability Scale (SUS), providing a structured evaluation of the system’s usability while focusing on the training modules’ specific features and objectives. This ensured a comprehensive assessment of both general and application-specific usability. In addition to the customized post-tests, the NASA-TLX (Task Load Index) method was employed to evaluate participants’ perceived workload during the training sessions [16]. NASA-TLX is commonly utilized in similar studies, and its inclusion in this study provided a valuable benchmark. Table 16 presents the specific questions used in the NASA-TLX assessment, offering detailed insights into the factors influencing participants’ workload perceptions.

Unlike the original 20-point scale of NASA-TLX, we used a simplified 10-point scale to make the workload assessment more accessible for participants. The NASA-TLX survey measured six dimensions: Mental Demand, Physical Demand, Temporal Demand, Effort, Frustration, and Performance. Participants rated their workload based on these dimensions, providing a deeper understanding of the cognitive and physical demands experienced during the training.

Finally, the Post-Test Feedback Survey allowed participants to provide qualitative feedback through three open-ended questions. This survey captured detailed insights into

TABLE 14. Nasa-TLX scaling.

Item	Endpoints	Description
Mental Demand	1-10 Low/High	How much mental and perceptual activity was required?
Physical Demand	1-10 Low/High	How much physical activity was required?
Temporal Demand	1-10 Low/High	How much time pressure did you feel due to the rate or pace at which the task occurred?
Performance	1-10 High/Low	How successful do you think you were in accomplishing the goals the task set by the experimenter?
Effort	1-10 Low/High	How hard did you have to work to accomplish your level of performance?
Frustration Level	1-10 Low/High	How insecure, discouraged, irritated, stressed and annoyed versus secure, gratified, content, relaxed and complacent did you feel during the task?

TABLE 15. Post-test feedback survey.

#	Survey Question
1	What did you like most about the training?
2	What improvements would you suggest for future training sessions?
3	Any other comments or feedback?

their experiences and suggestions for improving the platform. Table 15 lists the specific open-ended questions included in the survey, providing a structured framework for collecting participant feedback. Following the completion of the tests, the collected data, along with insights from the SUS-inspired post-tests and NASA-TLX analysis, was thoroughly compiled and evaluated. These combined methods ensured a comprehensive understanding of the platform’s effectiveness and areas for future refinement.

4) TEST GROUP SELECTION

The study included 22 participants selected to ensure diverse representation of professional roles, age groups, and prior XR experience levels. The majority were trainee engineers and technicians, aligning with the study’s focus on early-career professionals in technical fields. This group allowed an evaluation of the system’s effectiveness in skill-building and training for individuals at the start of their careers, while a

TABLE 16. Demographic breakdown.

Role	Participant	Age (YA)	AGE(A)	PRE-XR (NO)	PRE-XR (YES)
Trainee Engineer	13	13	0	5	8
Professional Engineer	5	5	0	1	4
Trainee Technician	3	1	2	1	2
Professional Technician	1	0	1	1	0

smaller group of experienced professionals provided comparative insights.

Most participants were young adults (YA), reflecting the goal of targeting those in the early stages of their professional journeys. Adults(A) with more experience offered valuable perspectives on how the system met the needs of both novice and experienced users. Additionally, prior XR experience varied, with some participants having professional or personal exposure to XR, while others had none. This diversity enabled the assessment of the system’s accessibility for beginners and its suitability for more experienced users.

By including participants with varying expertise, age, and familiarity with XR, the study provided a comprehensive evaluation of the training system. This diverse participant pool ensured robust feedback, offering insights into the system’s usability, adaptability, and potential to enhance industrial training. Table 16 shows the demographic breakdown of the participants.

B. ANALYSIS OF THE VALIDATION RESULTS

The tests revealed valuable insights into participants’ performance across scenarios, their satisfaction, and the learning outcomes achieved. Results indicated noticeable improvements in knowledge and practical skills, with scenario performance varying by complexity. High satisfaction levels reflected positive engagement and user experience. The learning outcomes confirmed the training effectively combined theory and hands-on practice, making it a meaningful tool for skill development.

1) ANALYSIS OF THE TEST GROUP

The validation study involved a diverse participant group categorized by age, prior XR experience, and professional roles. Among them, 86.36% were young adults aged 18 to 25, while 13.64% were adults aged 26 and older. This distribution highlighted the study’s emphasis on early-career professionals, particularly young adults who, due to their limited experience, were anticipated to benefit most from the immersive training modules.

The validation study involved a diverse participant group categorized by age, prior XR experience, and professional

roles. Most participants were young adults aged 18 to 25, while others were adults aged 26 and above. This distribution aligned with the study’s focus on early-career professionals, particularly young adults expected to gain significantly from the immersive training modules.

FIGURE 8. XR experience distribution.

Regarding professional roles, the majority (81.82%) were trainee engineers and technicians, consisting of 13 trainee engineers (59.09%) and 5 trainee technicians (22.73%). This group aligned with the study’s emphasis on early-career professionals and tested the platform’s capability to bridge theoretical knowledge and practical skills effectively. Meanwhile, a smaller proportion (18.18%) consisted of professional engineers and technicians, with 3 professional engineers (13.64%) and 1 professional technician (4.55%).

FIGURE 9. Role distribution.

The diversity in participant characteristics ensured a comprehensive evaluation of the platform, highlighting its adaptability and usability across different levels of expertise and professional roles. By integrating feedback from participants with varying roles, ages, and XR familiarity, the study provided valuable insights into the platform’s performance and areas for potential improvement.

2) ANALYSIS OF THE TRAINING DURATION

The literature review reveals that XR-based training, particularly using VR, has varying effects on training duration compared to traditional methods. Some studies (e.g., [4] and [8]) indicate that XR may slightly increase training time due to its interactive and detailed nature, while others ([15] and our study) demonstrate that XR significantly reduces training duration, especially for complex tasks. These differences depend on the design of XR systems, the users’ experience levels, and the scope of the training. Thus, whether

TABLE 17. Average duration experiences on literature.

Article	Traditional Training	XR Training
Wolfartsberger et. al.[8]	221 seconds	274 seconds
Zigart et. al. 2023 [4]	10.08 minutes	12.43 minutes
Pratticò, F. G., & Lamberti, F.[15]	90.7 minutes	36.3 minutes
Our Study	120 minutes	61.43 minutes

XR saves time or extends it should be evaluated within the specific context of its application.

FIGURE 10. Average minute by role.

The average completion time for all participants was 61.43 minutes, a significant improvement compared to the 120 minutes typically required by traditional methods. This highlights the platform’s ability to streamline training without compromising the quality of instruction.

Participants’ roles and prior experience played a key role in their completion times. Professional engineers and technicians completed the modules faster, averaging 58 minutes, benefiting from their prior technical knowledge and familiarity with real-world scenarios. In contrast, trainee engineers and technicians required slightly more time, averaging 61.62 and 60.20 minutes respectively. This difference underscores the learning curve faced by early-career professionals as they adapt to the system, particularly in more complex scenarios.

Individual performance also varied significantly. The fastest completion time, at 41 minutes, was achieved by a professional engineer with prior XR experience, demonstrating the advantages of both technical expertise and familiarity with immersive environments. Conversely, the longest time of 76 minutes was recorded by a trainee with no prior exposure to XR.

3) ANALYSIS OF PRE AND POST TEST PERFORMANCE

The pre- and post-test performance analysis highlighted the effectiveness of the training modules in enhancing participants’ knowledge and skills. Before the training, the average

FIGURE 11. Training duration per participant.

pre-test score across all participants was 14.09, indicating a limited understanding of the training content. After completing the modules, post-test scores showed significant improvement, with an average score of 65.9, demonstrating the system’s success in achieving measurable learning outcomes.

When analyzed by professional roles, distinct patterns emerged. Trainee engineers started with the lowest average pre-test score of 0.76, reflecting their limited prior knowledge. However, their post-test scores increased significantly to an average of 60.76, showing that the training effectively bridged knowledge gaps. Trainee technicians displayed moderate familiarity with the training material, scoring an average of 16 on the pre-test. Their post-test scores improved to 62.50, indicating steady gains in knowledge and understanding throughout the training.

Professional participants entered the training with a stronger baseline knowledge, as reflected in their higher pre-test scores. Professional engineers, for example, began with an average pre-test score of 53.33 and improved to 80 on the post-test, highlighting the system’s ability to further enhance the expertise of experienced users. Similarly, professional technicians achieved notable improvements, underscoring the training’s effectiveness in developing practical, hands-on skills across varying levels of prior experience.

These results underscore the ability of the training modules to cater to both novice and experienced participants, bridging knowledge gaps and reinforcing existing expertise.

Overall, the average improvement in scores was 51.81 points, indicating substantial cognitive and skill-based gains across all participant groups. Safety-related tasks and system operations emerged as areas of significant improvement, particularly for trainees, who demonstrated the most notable progress.

The data reveals a clear progression in participant performance across different questions before and after training. For instance, in the first question, 12 participants improved their understanding, transitioning to a higher level of competence. Similar patterns are observed in subsequent questions; in the third question, 11 participants demonstrated notable advancement post-training. This consistent upward movement indicates the effectiveness of the intervention in

FIGURE 12. Number of people at each level for each question.

TABLE 18. Nasa-TLX results.

Workload	Value
Low	0-0,9
Medium	1,0-2,9
Somewhat high	3,0-4,9
High	5,0-7,9
Very High	8,0-10,0

enhancing participants’ skills and understanding across all assessed areas.

4) ANALYSIS OF NASA-TLX TEST RESULTS

To begin with, although the NASA-TLX assessment is conducted during the Post-Test Phase, its detailed explanation is provided under a separate heading for enhanced clarity.

A total of 22 participants participated in the NASA-TLX survey, which evaluates workload on a 10-point scale. The results are grouped into five categories: Low (0–0.9), Medium (1.0–2.9), Somewhat High (3.0–4.9), High (–7.9), and Very High (8.0–10.0). These categories provide a clear and structured way to interpret the level of effort and demand experienced. With an average score of 3.91, the survey results are categorized as “Somewhat High,” indicating a moderate workload intensity based on the defined scale.

According to the workload categories, participants rated mental demand as the highest factor, with an average score of 6.95 out of 10, placing it in the “High” range. This shows that the tasks required a significant amount of thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving. While this level of mental effort is beneficial for learning and skill development, it also suggests that some aspects of the training could be simplified to reduce unnecessary complexity, especially for participants with less experience.

Physical demand scored 3.45 out of 10, categorized as “Somewhat high,” meaning the tasks involved minimal physical effort. This aligns with the focus of the training, which emphasized mental engagement over physical activity. Temporal demand, or the sense of time pressure, scored just 2.0 out of 10, placing it in the “Medium” range. This indicates that participants did not feel rushed, thanks to the

well-paced structure of the tasks, allowing them to focus on learning at a comfortable pace.

The effort dimension scored 6.27 out of 10, also in the “High” range, reflecting the amount of concentration and perseverance participants needed to complete the training. While this is expected for challenging tasks, it suggests there’s room to ease the mental load in future iterations for a smoother learning experience. On the positive side, frustration levels were relatively low, with a score of 2.5 out of 10, categorized as “Medium.” This indicates that participants generally felt supported and did not experience significant stress or discouragement during the training.

FIGURE 13. Nasa TLX results.

Overall, the average workload score of 3.91 falls in the “Somewhat high” range. While the mental demand and effort required were notable, low scores for time pressure and frustration show that the training was well-structured and supportive. This balance suggests the training provided a meaningful challenge without being overwhelming, with opportunities for small adjustments to further improve the experience.

A closer look at the minimum and maximum values for each NASA-TLX category reveals distinct variations among participants. Mental Demand ranged from about 5 to 8, reflecting differing levels of perceived cognitive challenge. Physical Demand spanned approximately 2 to 4, indicating a moderate range of physical interaction within the VR environment. Temporal Demand varied from 1 to 3, suggesting that while most participants felt little time pressure, a few operated under slightly tighter constraints. Effort scores were observed between 5 and 8, underscoring the intensity with which participants approached the tasks. Performance typically fell within the 2 to 4 range, indicating that most users felt capable of accomplishing the assigned procedures. Finally, Frustration ranged from about 1 to 4, suggesting that some participants occasionally found the scenarios challenging, but most felt adequately supported throughout.

When examining demographic factors—such as XR experience (YES/NO), occupation (Engineer/Technician), and age group (A/YA)—our sample showed only limited shifts in average workload scores, typically in the range of

0.2–0.5 points. This indicates that these variables did not strongly influence how participants perceived the overall workload.

5) ANALYSIS OF SATISFACTION

The satisfaction analysis aimed to understand participants’ overall experience with the training modules. Using a 5-point Likert scale, participants rated different aspects of the system, which resulted in an overall average satisfaction score of 4.15. The immersive and realistic nature of the VR environment stood out as the most highly rated feature, scoring 4.4/5. Participants particularly valued this realism for making the training more engaging and improving how well they retained the material.

The system’s ease of use received a positive score of 4/5, highlighting its accessibility, especially for those with no prior experience using XR technology. Participants also gave the clarity of instructions a solid 4/5, reflecting the training’s thoughtful and user-friendly design. However, the relevance of the training content to specific professional roles scored slightly lower at 3.72/5, suggesting that some scenarios could be better tailored to match individual job requirements. Similarly, hands-on practice opportunities scored 3.95/5, indicating that while participants appreciated the practical tasks, there’s room to expand these interactive elements.

FIGURE 14. Satisfaction by XR experience.

Those who were new to XR technology reported higher satisfaction levels compared to participants already familiar with such systems. Trainee engineers and technicians particularly appreciated the interactive and engaging nature of the training, while more experienced professionals valued its technical depth. However, the professionals also suggested that some modules could be enhanced to include more advanced skill-building tasks.

Overall, the analysis showed that the training experience was both engaging and effective. Participants consistently praised the system for its realistic scenarios, ease of use, and clear instructions, while also pointing to areas for potential refinement.

6) ANALYSIS OF SCENARIO PERFORMANCE

The performance data across the three scenarios revealed clear trends influenced by scenario complexity, participants’ roles, and their prior experience.

Scenario 1 (Health and Safety), which focused on health and safety, consistently resulted in the highest scores, with most participants scoring between 70 and 85 points. Its structured approach and straightforward tasks made it easy to follow, effectively reinforcing fundamental safety concepts. This scenario was particularly well-received, as the content was accessible and directly applicable to participants’ needs.

Scenario 2 (Introduction to Robotic Laboratory), centered on introducing robotic systems, showed more varied performance, with scores ranging from 60 to 80 points. Professional engineers excelled in this module, drawing on their technical knowledge to navigate tasks efficiently. However, trainee technicians and engineers required additional time and guidance, reflecting the steeper learning curve for those with less experience. While the scenario successfully built foundational knowledge of robotic systems, its technical nature posed challenges for less experienced participants, emphasizing the need for additional preparatory modules or step-by-step guidance to bridge the knowledge gap.

Scenario 3 (Robotic Maintenance), focused on robotic maintenance and troubleshooting, emerged as the most challenging. Scores for this scenario ranged from 50 to 75 points, with participants needing to diagnose and resolve system issues. This proved particularly difficult for trainees with limited technical experience. Although professionals performed relatively well, many participants indicated a need for more detailed, step-by-step guidance and support. This highlighted the importance of designing instructional materials that address varying levels of expertise.

FIGURE 15. Average scenario points for each role.

When performance was analyzed by professional roles, professional engineers consistently achieved the highest scores across all scenarios, performing particularly well in Scenario 1 and Scenario 3. Trainee technicians and engineers showed notable improvement in simpler tasks but struggled with the complexity of troubleshooting in Scenario 3. Meanwhile, professional technicians, despite their practical experience, recorded lower scores overall, pointing to

potential gaps in familiarity with more advanced technical concepts.

Age and prior experience with XR also played a role in performance trends. Adults aged 26 and older outperformed younger participants (18–25 years) in Scenario 2, demonstrating their ability to apply prior knowledge effectively. Participants with XR experience consistently scored higher in simpler scenarios, like Scenario 1, but faced similar challenges to novice users in the more complex Scenario 3. This suggests that having a solid foundation of technical knowledge was more critical for success in advanced tasks than XR familiarity alone.

FIGURE 16. Average scenario points.

In the first scenario, focused on health and safety, participants scored the highest with an average of 72 points due to its straightforward tasks. The second scenario, involving robotic systems, had a lower average score of 60 points, reflecting the technical challenges. The third scenario, focused on robotic maintenance and troubleshooting, was the most difficult, with an average score of 54 points. These results show how performance varied with the complexity of each scenario and the support needed for more advanced tasks.

V. DISCUSSION

The training system demonstrated significant success in enhancing participants' knowledge and skills through its immersive modules. One of the key outcomes of the study was a noticeable reduction in training duration, with an average completion time of 61.43 minutes—substantially shorter than the 120 minutes typically required by traditional methods. This highlights the system's ability to streamline complex training processes while maintaining the quality of instruction. However, comparisons with the findings in the literature suggest that there are opportunities for further enhancements to align the system more closely with best practices in XR-based training.

Although the system effectively reduced training times, some studies have shown that XR can, in certain cases, increase training duration [4], [8]. For example, this has been attributed to the detailed and interactive nature of XR environments or the initial learning curve participants face when adapting to immersive systems. On the other hand, optimized XR implementations in some studies have achieved

even greater time reductions. This variability underscores the importance of refining the system further, such as by modularizing scenarios or customizing learning paths to better suit individual participant needs.

One improvement could be the inclusion of preparatory simulations to help participants become more comfortable with the immersive environment before beginning formal training sessions [12]. Research suggests that such pre-education activities, like trial runs in virtual environments, can help reduce cognitive load and improve familiarity with XR systems. By providing participants with an opportunity to explore the interface and basic mechanics in advance, the adjustment period during formal training could be shortened, leading to smoother and more effective experience.

Another valuable addition would be integrating real-time feedback during the training sessions. Currently, insights are gathered mainly through post-training surveys, which provide helpful but retrospective data. Adding real-time feedback mechanisms, such as visual, auditory, or haptic cues, could allow participants to address challenges as they arise. This would not only improve task accuracy but also enhance engagement and support dynamic adjustments throughout the training. Real-time guidance could play a key role in making the experience more interactive and tailored to participants' immediate needs.

Incorporating gamification elements into the training system can enhance user motivation and engagement by providing tangible recognition through rewards, points, badges, or achievements for task completion and improvement, fostering a sense of accomplishment and competition among participants [7]. Additionally, structuring training into progressive levels, where advancement depends on mastering prior sections, ensures a step-by-step learning process that strengthens foundational skills before moving to complex tasks [7]. These strategies make the training experience more interactive, enjoyable, and goal-oriented, ultimately improving user satisfaction and learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the same training scenarios could have been conducted in an AR environment alongside VR to allow for a direct comparison between the two modalities. This approach would have provided deeper insights into how different immersive technologies impact user experience and training effectiveness.

Overall, this study identified and validated some of the limitations commonly observed in XR-based training applications through structured testing. By implementing a modular approach, we demonstrated a clear reduction in training duration, confirming that optimizing scenario structures can effectively shorten learning times without compromising instructional quality. Additionally, by employing NASA-TLX and SUS-like advanced surveys, we were able to assess participants' experiences before and after the training, providing a more comprehensive evaluation of cognitive load and usability. These findings reinforce the idea that structured and adaptive training methodologies can enhance the efficiency of XR-based learning environments. Through

these contributions, our study offers an incremental yet meaningful advancement to the existing body of research in XR training, providing insights that can help refine future immersive learning systems.

VI. LIMITATIONS

While the validation study provided valuable insights, there are areas for improvement that could enhance future iterations. The participant pool consisted of 22 individuals with diverse roles and varying levels of XR experience, which allowed for meaningful data collection. However, expanding the study to include a larger and more varied group of participants from different industries and experience levels could yield broader perspectives and more generalizable findings. Additionally, feedback mechanisms during the study relied primarily on post-training surveys. While these surveys offered valuable insights into user experiences and learning outcomes, incorporating real-time feedback during the training sessions could allow for immediate adjustments to address participant challenges, enhancing both the training experience and system adaptability.

The study primarily focused on short-term outcomes, such as knowledge acquisition and skill development during the training sessions. While these are important metrics, examining the long-term retention of skills and their application in real-world industrial settings would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the system's effectiveness. Follow-up evaluations could help assess whether participants are able to apply what they learned in practical scenarios and identify areas where additional support may be beneficial.

Although the system provided visual and auditory feedback to guide participants throughout the training, the absence of haptic feedback limited the overall user experience. This lack of tactile feedback reduces learning efficiency and diminishes the long-term retention of acquired skills. Tactile interaction plays a crucial role in skill-based training, especially in tasks requiring fine motor control or realistic object manipulation. The integration of haptic feedback in future iterations could enhance immersion, improve the transferability of skills to real-world applications, and further optimize training effectiveness.

These limitations are inherent aspects to be addressed in future studies. By focusing on these considerations, the training system can be refined to better accommodate the diverse needs of participants, improving its overall effectiveness and usability in a scientifically grounded way.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The training system proved to be highly effective in providing immersive and interactive learning experiences for industrial applications. By integrating VR and AR technologies, it allowed participants to engage with realistic scenarios that improved their knowledge, task proficiency, and overall engagement. One of the standout results was the significant reduction in training duration, with an average time of 61.43 minutes compared to the traditional 120-minute aver-

age. This highlights how the system successfully streamlined complex training processes without compromising quality.

The system catered to a wide range of participants, from those with limited technical expertise to those already familiar with XR technologies. According to the NASA-TLX survey results, the workload was rated as "Somewhat High," with mental demand being the most notable factor, scoring 6.95 out of 10. This reflects the cognitive complexity of the tasks, especially for less experienced users. However, physical and temporal demands were much lower, scoring 3.45 and 2.0 out of 10, respectively, suggesting that the training was well-paced and did not require excessive physical effort. Effort levels were rated at 6.27, indicating that participants were meaningfully engaged, while frustration levels remained relatively low at 2.5, showing that the training environment was supportive and manageable.

Looking ahead, several enhancements are planned to make the system even better. Software improvements will focus on enhancing the user experience by adding features like voice-guided instructions and an AI-powered chatbot. These additions aim to give participants instant support during their training, making the experience smoother and more interactive. Refinements to the scenarios will also ensure that content is better tailored to the specific needs of participants, addressing challenges highlighted in the feedback.

Additionally, future research will involve conducting the same training scenarios in an AR environment alongside VR, allowing for a direct comparison of the two modalities in terms of user experience and training effectiveness. This comparative study will provide deeper insights into how different immersive technologies influence learning outcomes and participant engagement.

The user interface (UI) will be upgraded to be more intuitive and visually appealing. Inspired by insights from existing research, the training modules will be further customized to match the expertise levels of users. For beginners, step-by-step guidance will provide a structured and supportive experience, while advanced users will benefit from a more open-ended environment that encourages independent exploration and problem-solving. By tailoring the training to individual skill levels, the system can offer a more personalized and effective learning experience.

Future studies will aim to involve a more diverse group of participants, including a broader range of demographics and industrial settings, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the system's adaptability and effectiveness. Additional features such as haptic feedback and modular training paths will also be explored to further enhance the user experience and make the system even more flexible and impactful.

In summary, the training system has shown great potential for improving industrial training processes by combining realistic scenarios, effective pacing, and meaningful engagement. With planned updates to the user experience, interface, and scenario design, the system is set to deliver even greater value in future applications. This study represents an incremental yet meaningful contribution to the existing

body of research in XR-based training, further advancing the understanding of immersive learning methodologies and their practical applications.

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